

FERROUS ASCORBATE IN PREGNANCY: INSIGHTS FROM A REAL-WORLD PRESCRIPTION EVENT MONITORING (PEM) STUDY

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Article Received on 05 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Nov. 2025,
Article Published on 01 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1780203>

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How to cite this Article: Rajvee A. Soni*, Dr. Ashok D. Agrawal¹, Dr. Mayur R. Bhurat¹, Aishwarya M. Agale¹, Puja R. Khodpe¹, Premjit G. Pawar¹, Dr. Ashish Wagh², Dimpal D. Maurya³ (2025). Ferrous Ascorbate In Pregnancy: Insights From A Real-World Prescription Event Monitoring (Pem) Study. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 14(12), 1331–1336.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is a common and significant public health concern during pregnancy, contributing to adverse maternal and fetal outcomes. Ferrous ascorbate, a combination of ferrous iron and ascorbic acid, offers enhanced bioavailability and improved gastrointestinal tolerability compared with conventional iron salts. This prescription-event monitoring (PEM) study aimed to generate real-world evidence on the safety and effectiveness of ferrous ascorbate in pregnant Indian women with IDA. **Methods:** This prospective, observational, non-interventional study included 126 pregnant women diagnosed with IDA who received ferrous ascorbate (Furr CR/Furr XT) according to the treating physician's discretion. Baseline demographic data, clinical characteristics, dosing details, and hemoglobin (Hb) values were recorded. Hb levels were reassessed after 4 weeks to determine treatment efficacy. Safety was evaluated through

adverse events (AEs) reported during the same period. Data analysis included descriptive statistics and paired t-tests to compare pre- and post-treatment Hb values. **Results:** Participants had a mean age of 27.92 ± 4.71 years and a mean weight of 53.76 ± 8.89 kg. The baseline Hb was 9.14 ± 0.95 g/dL. Following 4 weeks of ferrous ascorbate therapy, Hb increased significantly to 10.20 ± 0.98 g/dL, with a mean rise of 1.06 ± 0.03 g/dL ($p < 0.001$).

Consistent improvements were observed across all trimesters. The treatment was well tolerated; only 7 patients (5.5%) experienced mild AEs—constipation, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, or insomnia. No serious AEs were reported. **Conclusion:** Ferrous ascorbate (Furr CR/Furr XT of Corona Remedies Ltd., Ahmedabad) demonstrated significant improvement in Hb levels within 4 weeks and exhibited a favorable safety profile. These real-world findings support its effectiveness and tolerability as an oral iron therapy for managing IDA in pregnancy.

KEYWORDS: Iron deficiency anemia, Pregnancy, Ferrous ascorbate, Prescription-event monitoring (PEM).

INTRODUCTION

Iron deficiency anemia is a common nutritional problem during pregnancy, affecting both maternal and fetal health, including complications like preterm birth, low birth weight, and maternal fatigue.^[1] It's a major public health problem in developing countries. To counter these risks, iron supplementation is commonly recommended. However, the choice of iron supplement is critical due to varying levels of bioavailability, efficacy, and tolerability among different formulations.^[2] Ferrous ascorbate, a combination of ferrous iron and ascorbic acid, has gained attention due to its enhanced bioavailability compared to other iron supplements.^[3] The presence of ascorbic acid helps in converting ferric iron to its more absorbable ferrous form, facilitating superior iron absorption in the gastrointestinal tract.^[4] This formulation also tends to cause fewer gastrointestinal side effects, improving patient compliance, which is often a challenge with traditional iron salts like ferrous sulfate and ferrous fumarate. Other common iron supplements, such as ferrous sulfate and iron polymaltose, although effective in treating anemia, are often associated with poor absorption and increased gastrointestinal discomfort.^[5] Chelated iron and liposomal iron, though more advanced in terms of bioavailability, are costlier and not always accessible. Ferrous ascorbate, therefore, strikes a balance between higher absorption efficiency and affordability, making it a potentially superior option for pregnant women.^[6] Thus, to further strengthen the data suggesting good efficacy and safety of ferrous ascorbate in pregnancy and to gather real-world clinical practice events on safety and efficacy of ferrous ascorbate in Indian patients with pregnancy, this study was planned.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a prospective, observational, noncomparative, non-interventional, prescription event monitoring (PEM) study.^[7] Data were collected from single centres from the health records of 126 patients with iron deficiency anemia in pregnancy who were administered Ferrous ascorbate (Furr CR/Furr XT, Corona Remedies Ltd., Ahmedabad) as per the treating physician's judgement and the product's prescribing information. Following details were recorded in to the CRF: patient's age, weight, co-morbidities, details of Ferrous ascorbate administration (total dose, method & duration of administration) along with baseline Hb values. These laboratory parameters assessed after 4 weeks of Ferrous ascorbate administration and data recorded in to the CRF. No additional investigational were done beyond the standard clinical practice for the purpose of study.

Safety was assessed from adverse events reported within 4 weeks post Ferrous ascorbate administration. Treatment efficacy was assessed by change in Hb from baseline to 4 weeks after treatment.

Statistics

We performed a descriptive analysis of the data. Continuous variables are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.). Categorical variables are presented as proportions. Students paired t test was used for change in Hb and p value <0.05 was considered statically significant. Missing data was not considered for calculating percentages. The statistical analysis was performed using SAS software package.

RESULTS

Demographic and baseline characteristics

Total 126 adult patients with mean age of 27.92 ± 4.71 years, weight of 53.76 ± 8.89 kg and mean baseline Hb of 9.14 ± 0.95 gm/dl were treated with Ferrous Ascorbate. Total 30.95% patients were having co-morbid conditions (diabetes mellitus, pregnancy induced hypertension and obesity) and were receiving disease-specific treatment.

Table 1: Baseline demographic variables of study participants.

Parameters	Over all	Trimester wise		
		1 st trimester	2 nd trimester	3 rd trimester
Total number of patients (n)	126	77	30	19
Age (years; mean \pm S.D.)	27.92 ± 4.71	27.76 ± 4.57	27.46 ± 4.89	29.31 ± 4.96

Weight (kg; mean \pm S.D.)	53.76 \pm 8.89	53.03 \pm 8.17	56.63 \pm 9.90	54.89 \pm 9.89
Co-morbidities (n ;%)	39 (30.95%)	21 (16.66%)	12 (9.52%)	6 (4.76%)
Hypertension (n ;%)	4 (3.17%)	2 (1.85%)	1 (0.79%)	1 (0.79%)
Diabetes Mellitus (n ;%)	7 (5.55%)	5 (3.96%)	1(0.79%)	1 (0.79%)
Obesity (n ;%)	28 (22.22%)	14 (11.11%)	10 (7.93%)	4 (3.17%)

Assessment of efficacy

Change in Hb as evaluated in 126 patients. There were significantly increased Hb from 9.14 \pm 0.95 gm/dl at baseline to 10.20 \pm 0.95 gm/dl with mean difference of 1.06 \pm 0.03 gm/dl (CI 95%: 0.8205 to 1.2995, $p < 0.001$) at 4 weeks post-treatment the data are shown in table 2.

Table 2: Assessment of efficacy of Ferrous Ascorbate.

Patient Categories	N	Baseline Hb (gm/dl)	Hb after Ferrous ascorbate (gm/dl)	Mean change in Hb from baseline (gm/dl)	P' value Vs baseline
Over all	126	9.14 \pm 0.95	10.20 \pm 0.98	1.06 \pm 0.03	$p < 0.01$
Trimester wise					
1st trimester	77	9.08 \pm 0.92	10.08 \pm 0.96	1 \pm 0.04	$p < 0.01$
2nd trimester	30	9.28 \pm 1.10	10.54 \pm 1.11	1.26 \pm 0.01	$p < 0.01$
3rd trimester	19	9.14 \pm 0.82	10.20 \pm 0.72	1.06 \pm 0.01	$p < 0.01$

Safety assessment

Ferrous ascorbate was well tolerated in majority of patients. Only 7 patients (5.5%) reported adverse events (Table 3)]. There were no serious adverse events reported.

Table 2: Assessment of Safety of Ferrous Ascorbate.

Patient Categories	N	Constipation	Vomiting	Nausea	Diarrhea	Insomnia
1st trimester	4	2	-	1	-	1
2nd trimester	2	1	1	-	-	-
3rd trimester	1	-	-	-	1	-
Total	7	3	1	1	1	1

DISCUSSION

In settings where anemia is a public health concern, WHO recommends oral iron supplementation for women. Oral iron remains the first-line treatment due to its affordability, ease of administration, and widespread availability. Ferrous ascorbate, a highly bioavailable oral iron formulation, is commonly used due to its improved absorption compared to

traditional iron salts like ferrous sulfate. The ascorbate component enhances iron solubility, improving intestinal absorption and reducing unabsorbed iron that can cause gastrointestinal side effects. However, despite its benefits, oral iron therapy is often hindered by gastrointestinal side effects and patient non-compliance due to prolonged treatment duration. While oral iron remains the preferred option, IV iron is used in cases where rapid Hb correction is necessary, such as in severe anemia or intolerance to oral therapy.^[10,11& 12]

This study was carried out to gather real-world clinical practice events on safety and efficacy of Ferrous ascorbate in Indian female patients with pregnancy. In this study we found that there was significant increased in Hb levels from baseline (1.06 ± 0.03 gm/dl; $p < 0.001$) at 4 weeks post Ferrous ascorbate administration. Results of our study are well supported by findings of several randomized, controlled studies involving Ferrous ascorbate as treatment arm. In a randomized, comparative study by Chavan S et al., mean Hb rise with Ferrous ascorbate was compared with Hb rise with ferrous sulphate, and iron hydroxide polymaltose.^[2]

Similarly in our study we found, a consistent improvement in Hb levels across all trimesters. The treatment was well tolerated, only 7 (5.55%) patients developed adverse events namely constipation, vomiting, nausea, diarrhoea and insomnia. There were no serious adverse events reported.

Limitations of study

Our study is only single centre study. Various observational studies have related different levels of TSAT and serum ferritin. However, as data on serum ferritin and TSAT was not available for all the patients in our study, we were not able to analyse these parameters for efficacy.

CONCLUSION

Ferrous ascorbate was safe and well tolerated without any serious adverse event. It was found to increase Hb significantly in a shorter period of time in patients with iron deficiency anemia in pregnancy. Our study further strengthens the clinical trial findings of good safety and efficacy of Ferrous ascorbate in patients with pregnancy in real-world clinical practice.

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